

PROFESSIONALIZING THE SPA INDUSTRY IN CALAMBA CITY

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to professionalize the spa industry in Calamba City tourism by determining the degree of compliance with DOT regulations for spa operation and maintenance. For this study, a descriptive quantitative research design was employed. Structured questionnaires were employed to gather numerical data from a sample population. Findings revealed that the assessment of the respondents in compliance with certification requirements, regulation requirements, customer-centric policies, and practices is slightly implemented / slightly evident. The study suggests that as spa establishments operate for longer periods, there is a slight tendency for them to have better certification, and regulation status, implement customer-centric policies and have better-established protocols and practices. The size of the spa establishment may not significantly influence its certification status, regulatory compliance, or customer-centric policies, and practices. Spa businesses with larger client bases may be more motivated to invest in accreditation and quality assurance measures to meet the needs and expectations of their clientele. The study revealed that established businesses tend to exhibit better adherence to regulations, indicating the importance of experience in navigating regulatory frameworks. While the spa industry in Calamba City shows promising signs of stability and efforts towards compliance, there is a clear imperative for targeted interventions to professionalize the sector. By addressing gaps in regulatory adherence, enhancing customer-centric policies, and providing support for businesses seeking accreditation, stakeholders can work towards elevating the standards of the spa industry and fostering sustained growth and development in Calamba City.

Keywords: *Professionalizing, Spa Industry, Calamba City, Massage*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine spa industry is a growing sector with significant potential for economic growth and tourism development. With its rich natural resources and cultural heritage, the nation possesses the potential to become a prominent wellness tourism destination (Brillantes-Turvill, 2021). Furthermore, the spa industry's sustainability efforts are gaining momentum globally, focusing on eco-friendly practices, responsible sourcing, and community engagement (SpaChina, 2021).

After the COVID-19 pandemic, the industry has experienced a surge in popularity not only in the Philippines but around the world as well. According to Research and Markets Ltd. (n.d.), the growing awareness among people regarding their health and wellbeing contributed to the surge in popularity of the spa industry. Moreover, the growth is attributed to several factors, including body condition, affordability, and relaxation. A lot of Filipinos decided to open their own spa facility to take advantage of the opportunity of increased popularity and demand for the service sector. According to Atienza et al. (2014), spas became a major factor that affects how people manage their health, as well as how they socialize, practice their spirituality, travel, and go to work.

However, the spa industry in the Philippines is teeming with potential yet laden with challenges that hinder its professionalization. It can be observed that after a few months or a year, new spa outlets are seen, the business closes, or new management takes over. From this observation, questions can be raised about its professionalization, which is always at risk. The same can be observed in the spa industry in Calamba City. People see that there is a lack of professional autonomy which results in limited professional development and that being a massage therapist is an unattractive career prospect. This affects professionalization of the spa industry in Calamba City.

Research Questions

The study described the processes of professionalizing spa industry in Calamba City. Particularly, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the current condition of the spa industry in Calamba City in terms of:
 - a. Certification
 - b. Regulation Requirements
 - c. Customer – centric policies
 - d. Practices
2. What are the barriers faced by the respondents on the following:
 - a. Certification
 - b. Regulation Requirements
 - c. Customer – centric policies
 - d. Practices
3. From the findings of the study, what policy guidelines can be proposed to professionalize the spa industry in Calamba City?

METHODOLOGY

Scope and Limitations. This study is designed to delve into the processes of professionalizing the spa industry in Calamba City. The primary focus lies in capturing the perspectives and experiences of key stakeholders actively involved in the spa industry. However, the study recognizes the existence of potential biases in participants' responses, which may influence the research outcomes. Importantly, this study is confined to Calamba City only, and the findings may not be universally applicable to all regions within the country. The population included in the study is limited to businesses that offer spa/massage services only. Additionally, the study would not provide an exhaustive overview of all potential stakeholders within the spa industry.

Research Design. A descriptive quantitative research design was employed in this study. The quantitative research method would provide a comprehensive understanding of the professionalization processes in the spa industry in Calamba City. In the quantitative phase, validated structured questionnaires were employed to gather numerical data from a sample population. By employing quantitative methods, the researcher was able to quantify the prevalence of certain opinions, identify trends and was particularly valuable when seeking to understand the overarching trends and patterns within the industry.

Research Locale. The research was conducted in various spa establishments within Calamba City, Philippines. The selection of this location is based on its representation of the spa industry in terms of size. Calamba City's strategic location and status as an emerging metropolis make it a significant player in the spa industry's growth and development. Its accessibility, economic growth, and the increasing demand for wellness services create a conducive environment for the spa industry to thrive.

Population and Sampling Design. Purposive sampling method was employed. To identify spa massage centers in Calamba City, site visits and gathering of secondary data from the local government offices were conducted. The spa center selection was based on length of business operation, business size, and number of clients of the spa business. Five (5) spa centers were selected based on this inclusion criterion. Five (5) spa centers were selected based on the inclusion criteria. This would include selection of owners and managers of the spa center. Rank and file employees were also selected based on years of experience. Clients were selected based on convenience or availability during the time of data collection.

Research Instruments. Structured questionnaires were adapted to the Department of Tourism Revised Rules and Regulations to Govern Spa Establishments using the Likert Scale. The questionnaire was divided to two (2) parts. The first part profiled the respondents. The data resulting from the respondent profiling were used on the spa center selection. The second part determined the adherence to spa establishment standards of the spa industry in Calamba City. The second part of the questionnaire was also used as the basis of the researcher's observations. Field notes were added to address items that are not included in the questionnaire. The field notes were the product of questions directly asked by the researcher to the respondents.

The questionnaires were pre-tested and validated through pilot testing and expert reviews to ensure their reliability and validity. Cronbach's Alpha was used to ensure reliability and validity was ensured through context clarity and comprehensiveness of the questionnaires.

Data Gathering Procedure. For quantitative research, the questionnaires were administered in person to spa stakeholders, massage therapists, and clients in the selected spa establishments. In cases where in-person administration is not possible, online surveys were emailed to target participants. Secondary data and literatures were gathered to supplement substantial information to the research. Secondary data from the City Government of Calamba were requested.

Management and Treatment if Data. For quantitative data, descriptive statistics were used to analyze the responses obtained from the questionnaires.

Quantitative data from structured questionnaires underwent a comprehensive analysis employing various statistical measures.

1. **Weighted Mean:** The mean provided the average response for each questionnaire item. This was used to assess the spa industry in terms of adherence to DOT standards of spa establishments.

RESULTS

RQ #1 Current condition of the spa industry in Calamba City based on the DOT Revised Rules and Regulations to Govern the Accreditation of Spa Establishments

Data gathered from the DOT showed that no spa business involved in this study is accredited by the DOT. This means that no secondary data was obtained to know the current condition of the spa industry in Calamba City in terms of certification, regulation, customer-centric policies, and practices. No secondary data for the current condition of the certification and regulation because the involved businesses are not accredited. No secondary data for the customer-centric policies and practices because no entity is regulating the business operations.

The DOT also informed the researcher that under the Tourism Act of 2009 or R.A. 9593, the Spa category will fall under Secondary Tourism Enterprises. Thus, their application for DOT Accreditation is only voluntary. No equivalent penalty is established for non-application for accreditation. To supplement information in this section, the researcher opted to do observation using the questionnaires. (Table 1)

Table 1. Researchers Observation for Spa Respondents

Spa	Dimensions	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Spa 1	Certification	3.67	Slightly implemented / evident
	Regulation Requirements	4.38	Slightly implemented / evident
	Customer – centric policies	4.50	Slightly implemented / evident
	Practices	4.00	Slightly implemented / evident
Spa 2	Certification	3.50	Indifferent
	Regulation Requirements	3.88	Slightly implemented / evident
	Customer – centric policies	3.17	Indifferent
	Practices	3.60	Slightly implemented / evident
Spa 3	Certification	3.50	Indifferent
	Regulation Requirements	3.38	Indifferent
	Customer – centric policies	3.00	Indifferent
	Practices	3.40	Indifferent
Spa 4	Certification	3.17	Indifferent
	Regulation Requirements	3.38	Indifferent
	Customer – centric policies	2.83	Indifferent
	Practices	3.40	Indifferent
Spa 5	Certification	3.17	Indifferent
	Regulation Requirements	2.88	Indifferent
	Customer – centric policies	2.67	Indifferent
	Practices	3.20	Indifferent

RQ # 2. Barriers faced by the spa industry based on DOT Revised Rules and Regulations to Govern the Accreditation of Spa Establishments

Table 2 shows the summary of barriers faced by the spa industry in Calamba City. The researcher analyzed the data to find commonality in the barriers faced by the spa industry in Calamba City answered by the respondents and the researcher's observation. The respondents believe that items slightly implemented and must be given extra attention so that the spa businesses can fully deliver proper services. The policy guidelines would revolve around these findings.

Table 2. Barriers faced by the spa industry based on DOT Revised Rules and Regulations to Govern the Accreditation of Spa Establishments

Dimensions	Source	Statements	Barrier
Certification	Stakeholder	Mayor's permit	There might be inconsistencies or lapses in compliance across the industry
	Stakeholder	In the case of corporation or partnership, a certified true copy of the Articles of Incorporation, or Articles of Partnership.	There might be instances where the documentation is incomplete or not fully compliant with regulatory standards
	Researcher	List of employees and trained therapists; and valid health certificate of all massage therapists duly issued by the proper authority	These requirements are not displayed well publicly on the spa establishments.
Regulation	Stakeholder	The spa is located in a safe and reputable location with clean, calm and relaxing environment	Spas are not situated in safe and reputable locations with appropriate ambiance
	Stakeholder	There is a high-powered generator capable of 7 providing full power in all areas of the establishment	Spas do not have a generator set that can be used during power outages.
	Researcher	There is a high-powered generator capable of providing full power in all areas of the establishment	Spas do not have a generator set that can be used during power outages.
Customer-centric policies	Stakeholder	There are separate, clean, and adequate public washrooms for male and female customers provided with running water and adequate toiletries	Spas do not have own washrooms for customer use
	Stakeholder	There is an adequate and secured parking space provided for customers/guests	Spas do not have adequate and secured parking space for customers/guests
	Researcher	There are facilities and provisions for the disabled.	No provisions to assist the disabled are present going to the spa establishments.
Practices	Stakeholder	Sanitation measures like cleaning sterilizing of equipment, robes, robes, sheets, blankets, pillow case, towels or other materials which may come in direct contact with the client's body shall be implemented.	There is a lack of sanitation practices in spas
	Stakeholder	Fire-fighting facilities and training shall be provided its employees	There is a lack of fire fighting equipment and training in spas
	Researcher	Display of Certificate of Accreditation and Sticker	The spa respondents are not accredited by the DOT.

DISCUSSION

1. Barriers on Certification

The study showed varying compliance with certification requirements, specifically the mayor's permit, and articles of incorporation or partnership. This ranked the lowest in certification requirements among the respondents. As for the researcher observation, the list of employees and trained therapists, and the valid health certificates of all massage therapists duly issued by the proper authority are not displayed in the establishment.

These documents are necessary to obtain accreditation. There may be spas that have not properly obtained the mayor's permit, but there may be others that have, demonstrating a lack of uniformity in the industry's adherence to this legislation. Spas may have a list of employees and trained therapists and may have obtained valid health certificates of all its massage therapists but not aware that it should be displayed.

This situation suggests a possible opportunity for improvement. It's possible that the rules need to be enforced more strictly or that spa owners need to be made more aware of the significance of these requirements. The lack of clear guidelines and standardized practices creates confusion among spa owners and therapists (Pang & Smith, 2017). It should be ensured that every spa in Calamba City complies with these requirements. This might guarantee consumer safety and high-quality services while still preserving a fair business climate.

2. Barriers on Regulatory Requirements

Compliance with safe and reputable location, and the availability of the generator ranked the lowest in the regulatory requirements among the respondents. As for the researcher observations, the availability of the generator also ranked the lowest.

Variations in compliance in terms of safety requirements could impact customer experience and business reputation negatively. Variations in compliance could be a result of various interpretations of the requirement. A more detailed description of this requirement should be observed. Other government references should be cited such as the national building code to make this requirement clearer. While regulations exist, their enforcement often lacks consistency and effectiveness (Zhang & Chen, 2018).

3. Barriers on Customer-centric Policies

In customer-centric policies, compliance in adequate and secured parking space, and adequacy of public washrooms ranked the lowest among the

respondents. Facilities and provisions for the disabled ranked the lowest for the researcher.

Most of the spa businesses are located in an area where there are little to no provision for parking. Parking on the roadside would put the customer vehicles in danger. Also, it is against the law in certain parts of Calamba City to park in non-designated parking areas. Also, majority of the spas does not have provisions for the disabled such as elevators to assist its disabled customers.

Securing adequate and secure parking, and consideration of the disabled customers will give the spas more advantage against its competitors.

4. Barriers on Practices

Sanitation measures and firefighting facilities and training ranked the lowest in practices among the respondents. The researcher observed that all spas does not display a certificate of accreditation and sticker in the spa establishments.

Sanitation should be a top priority in spa businesses since it is a service that requires direct contact with the customers. This will negatively affect the reputation and credibility of spa establishments if this is not strictly observed. Lack of or inconsistent sanitation measures probably resulted from lack of inspection from government entities.

Spa accreditation is voluntary. This might be the reason why there is no displayed certificate of accreditation and sticker in the spa establishments.

Conclusions

Derivable Conclusions from Research Data. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. The study revealed that established businesses tend to exhibit better adherence to regulations, indicating the importance of experience in navigating regulatory frameworks. However, there remains a notable variability in compliance levels across different aspects of spa operations which suggests a need for more uniform enforcement and support mechanisms. Furthermore, the findings highlight the importance of prioritizing customer-centric policies and amenities to enhance overall service quality and customer satisfaction. While efforts have been made to improve amenities and facilities, there is still room for enhancement to meet evolving customer expectations and preferences.

2. While the spa industry in Calamba City shows promising signs of stability and efforts towards compliance, there is a clear imperative for targeted interventions to professionalize the sector. By addressing gaps in regulatory adherence, enhancing customer-centric policies, and providing support for businesses seeking accreditation, stakeholders can work towards elevating the standards of the spa industry and fostering sustained growth and development in Calamba City.

The barriers of the spa industry in Calamba City are solvable. Reinforcement in education in terms of certification requirements is suggested. This would result in a higher percentage of compliance among existing businesses and to interested parties who wants to put up their own spa business. Regular audits and inspections would benefit both the business and customers as this would ensure compliance with the DOT standard. Creation of customer feedback mechanisms is suggested to improve existing customer-centric policies. Standardization is recommended to ensure that good practices are maintained and implemented while bad practices are removed from the operations.

Recommendations

Research and Policy Recommendations. Policy guidelines were recommended to the city government based on the identified barriers on certification, regulation, customer-centric policies, and practices experienced by the spa industry. The policy guidelines can be used by the LGU to formulate policies or regulations for the improvement of the spa industry in Calamba City.

Finally, The Tourism Act of 2009 or R.A. 9593, declares Spa category as a Secondary Tourism Enterprises. Hence, the accreditation for spa businesses is only voluntary.

1. **To the local government and relevant stakeholders.** It is recommended to make the accreditation for spa businesses mandatory. It is also recommended to include the accreditation in the requirements needed to obtain a business permit. Allocate resources for regular inspections, audits, and enforcement actions to ensure compliance with regulatory requirements. Collaborate with industry experts, academia, and business owners to develop comprehensive guidelines and standards and offer specialized training programs and certifications tailored to the needs of the spa industry in Calamba City.
2. **To the spa business owners.** Prioritize investment in training and development to ensure a high level of competence and professionalism among employees. Regularly review and update operational procedures and amenities to align with industry best practices and customer preferences. Collaborate with industry associations and regulatory bodies to stay informed about changes in regulations and accreditation requirements, and proactively work towards meeting and exceeding these standards.

3. **To the citizens of Calamba City.** Support local spa businesses that demonstrate a commitment to professionalism, quality, and regulatory compliance. Provide feedback to spa establishments to help them identify areas for improvement and enhance the overall customer experience. Stay informed about regulatory standards and encourage compliance within the community to promote a safe and reputable spa industry in Calamba City.
4. **To future researchers.** Conduct longitudinal studies to track the progress of the spa industry in Calamba City following the implementation of recommended interventions. Explore the impact of regulatory changes, training programs, and industry initiatives on the professionalization of the spa sector. Additionally, investigate consumer perceptions and preferences to identify emerging trends and inform future recommendations for enhancing the quality and competitiveness of spa services in the city.

Table 3: Policy guidelines to professionalize the spa industry in Calamba City

Area	Objective	Guidelines	Duration	Implementer	Resources Needed
Certification	1. Enhance compliance with accreditation standards set by the DOT 2. Improve documentation in mayor's permit and articles of incorporation or partnership, list of trained therapists, and valid health certificates	1. Encourage business owners to get DOT accreditation for their businesses. 2. Conduct workshops and training sessions on DOT accreditation requirements. 3. Assist to spa establishments in preparing documentation for accreditation.	6 months	LGU – Calamba	Trainers, training materials, citizen's charter, administrative support
Regulation	Improve adherence to regulatory standards outlined by the DOT specifically in spa location, and generator provisions of spas.	1. Establish a regulatory compliance task force to monitor and enforce adherence to regulations. 2. Conduct regular inspections and audits of spa establishments.	Continuous	LGU – Calamba	Regulatory experts, inspection resources, administrative support
Customer-Centric Policies	1. Enhance customer satisfaction and experience through improved amenities, services, and consideration of the disabled. 2. Provide adequate and secured parking space	1. Implement customer feedback mechanisms to identify areas for improvement. 2. Upgrade facilities to meet or exceed customer expectations. 3. Allocate a portion of the property for parking space or rent a lot for parking purposes	12 months	Business Owners	Customer feedback system, renovation resources
Practices	Ensure consistent implementation of best practices in spa operations	1. Develop standard operating procedures (SOPs) for key operational processes. 2. Provide ongoing training and re-training for staff on SOPs especially on sanitation and fire fighting practices.	Continuous	1. LGU – Calamba 2. Business Owners	Training materials, trainers, administrative support

Table 3 above presents the proposed policy guidelines to professionalize the spa industry in Calamba City, based on the findings of the study. First, to enhance certification, workshops and training sessions must be conducted to familiarize spa owners with the DOT accreditation standard. This effort aims to facilitate compliance by assisting establishments in preparing necessary documentation. Simultaneously, regulatory adherence can be improved by establishing a dedicated task force responsible for monitoring and enforcing DOT regulations. This entails conducting regular inspections and audits to ensure compliance with safety, hygiene, and operational standards. Furthermore, spa establishments should implement customer feedback mechanisms and invest in facility upgrades aligned with customer expectations. To ensure consistent implementation of best practices, standard operating procedures (SOPs), especially on sanitation must be developed and integrated into spa operations. Ongoing staff training and re-training initiatives will reinforce industry best practices, maintaining service quality and professionalism.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Voluntary Participation and Informed Consent

Participants' voluntary involvement in the study was paramount. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, outlining the purpose of the research, the procedures involved, and their rights. They were informed that they can withdraw from the study at any point without repercussions. This transparent communication ensured that participants are fully aware of their involvement and can make an informed decision about their participation.

Anonymity and Confidentiality

Preserving the confidentiality and anonymity of participants is essential in building trust. Personal identifiers such as names, addresses, and contact details **were not** collected, ensuring that participants' identities remain protected. Any information that could potentially reveal their identity were removed or anonymized in the research findings and reports. This approach safeguarded participants from any potential **harm**, or social repercussions related to their participation.

Truth and Accuracy

Maintaining truth and accuracy in the research process is fundamental. Data collection, analysis, and reporting were conducted diligently and objectively. Researchers refrained from bias, ensuring that the findings are a genuine reflection of participants' responses. Honest and transparent reporting, without distortion or manipulation of data, is essential for the credibility of the study.

Privacy Concerns and the Use of Codes

Privacy concerns were addressed by assigning codes or pseudonyms to participants during the data analysis and reporting phases. Instead of using real names, these codes were used consistently in all documents and records related to the research. This practice added an additional layer of confidentiality, further protecting participants' identities. Additionally, any sensitive information shared by participants were handled with utmost care and respect, emphasizing the importance of their privacy.

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